

ered at almost the same time as the nodal panicles. These side tillers developed from the most basal node of the main culm (Fig. 2). Total computed yield (0.3 t/ha) was derived mainly from nodal panicles (0.2 t/ha) and side tiller panicles (0.1 t/ha). Primary panicles yielded a comparatively low 0.02 t/ha.

The importance of nodal tiller pani-

cles is questionable, but they may have economic implications in dryland rainfed areas, especially where the rainy season is long but variable at anthesis. Subsistence farmers could benefit from seed production for next season's crop. Any yield in the event of a severe drought at flowering would benefit food and seed production. ■

2. Second nodal panicle and side tiller panicle on drought-stressed rice plant. IRRI.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Response of IR8 to zinc fertilizer

Z. H. Bhuiya, M. Idris, and M. J. Uddin, Soil Science Department, Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh

Zinc is considered an important limiting nutritional factor in Bangladesh rice production, especially where lands remain wet for long periods of the year and in calcareous soil zones. A simple fertilizer trial was carried out in a non-calcareous dark grey floodplain soil (order Inceptisol, suborder Aquept, and Subgroup Aeris Haplaquept) at BAU farm during the 1980 spring season.

IR8 was the test crop. Soil character-

istics were pH 6.3, organic carbon 1.67%, and available zinc 0.11 ppm. Treatments were control (no zinc application), application of 10 kg ZnSO₄/ha, and root-dipping in 2% ZnO suspension before transplanting.

At early growth stage, plants became stunted and tillering was reduced in the control plots. Growth in the zinc-treated plots was relatively better. Affected

plants recovered partially at a later growth stage but plant maturity was delayed by about 2 weeks. Although yields were relatively low in all plots, zinc application produced a marked yield increase over control (see table). The highest grain yield was recorded in ZnSO₄ treatment (130% increase over control). ■

Effect of zinc fertilizer on rice yield^a at Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control	Straw yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control
ZnSO ₄	2.04	130	3.04	112
ZnO	1.94	118	2.74	91
Control	0.89	—	1.44	—

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bOven-dry basis.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Observations on diseases of dryland rice in Brazil, March 1981

S. C. Mathur, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack-753006, India

Goinia (Goias), Campinas (São Paulo), and Cuiaba (Mato Grosso), extensive rice areas in central southeastern Brazil were visited by a traveling workshop on blast and dryland rice and monitoring tour of large dryland rice areas in Brazil. The workshop-tour was jointly organized by the Brazilian Government (CNPAP, Goiania, and EMPA, Cuiaba-MT), Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT, Colombia), and

the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) 12-19 March 1981.

The highly mechanized direct-seeded rice crop grown in acidic (pH about 4.0 to 5.0) soils with low water retention was found to be infected with varying severity by a number of fungal diseases. In the large rice areas in Mato Grosso, disease incidence was high (see table). In general, rice was in grain ripening or maturity stages and in some cases was being harvested. Diseases recorded were foliar blast, neck blast (*Pyricularia oryzae*), narrow brown leaf spot (*Sphaerulina oryzae*), leaf scald (*Rhynchosporium oryzae*), stack burn (*Alternaria padwickii*), sheath rot (*Acrocyndrium oryzae*), sheath blight (*Thanatephorus cucumeris*), and brown spot (*Helminthosporium oryzae*).

Because of a long drought (about 25 days), the crop in Campinas was generally poor and foliar blast was either absent or in a mild form. No other disease was observed. In uniform blast nursery trials, however, foliar blast was severe in irrigated crops.

Observations at the sites visited led to these conclusions:

- Three varieties under extensive cul-

Diseases of dryland rice in Mato Grosso, Brazil, 1981.

Site	Variety	Blast		Narrow brown leaf spot	Scald	Stack burn	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Glume blotch	Brown spot
		Foliar	Neck							
<i>Cuiaba</i>										
Umurama Farm	IAC 47	Severe	Severe (20-30%)	Severe	-	-	-	Mild	Moderate	Trace
Prata Farm	IAC 47 ^a IAC 25 IAC 164	Trace	Severe (20%)	-	Severe	-	-	Mild	-	-
Rondonopolis	Uniform Variety Trial, 18 entries	Trace	-	Mild	Moderate to severe	Moderate to severe	-	Moderate to severe	Moderate to severe	Mild
<i>Jaciara</i>										
Guarita Farm	IAC 47	-	Mild	Very severe (neck region affected)	Trace	-	-	Moderate	-	-
Expt. fields	UVT, 18 entries	Trace	Mild	-	Moderate	-	-	Moderate	-	-
Santa Fe Exp. Station EMPA	IAC 25 ^b	-	-	-	-	Moderate	-	-	Moderate	-
Chapada dos Guimaraes										
Estrella do Norte	IAC 47 ^c		Trace to mild	Moderate to severe (neck region affected)	Mild	-	Mild	Mild	Trace	Mild

^aDisease severe at early growth stage. ^bSprayed twice with BIM '75PM fungicide. ^cSprayed with Kitazin.

tivation — IAC 47, IAC 25, and IAC 164 — are highly susceptible to the fungal diseases observed.

- The incidence of one or more diseases was high at every site.
- Narrow brown leaf spot disease was found on the neck node, giving an appearance of neck blast, a symptom which so far has not been noticed in Asian countries.
- Typical white chaffy panicles due to neck blast were not observed, although some farms had a high

incidence — more than 20% — of neck infection, probably because of late infection.

- Spraying with tricyclalole [5-methyl-1, 2, 3-triazol (3,4-b)- benzo-thiazol] helped control blast but not stack burn.
- Most of the fungal diseases observed are known to be seed-borne. In many areas rice cultivation started in the last two to three years. Apparently, the diseases were introduced through seed and estab-

lished because of favorable weather conditions.

- No bacterial or viral diseases of rice were observed.

In the absence of disease-resistant varieties suitable for Brazilian conditions, the interim measures to minimize diseases are regular seed treatment with systemic fungicides, spraying the crop three times with fungicides having different active ingredients in rotation, and producing disease-free seed through plant protection. ■

Dose and application schedule of IBP granules to control rice blast

S. Kumar and J. P. Sharma, ICAR Research Complex for N. E. H. Region, Nagaland Centre, Medziphema - 797106, Nagaland, India

Rice neck blast (*Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.) causes yield losses in transplanted paddy of valleys and foothills of Nagaland. Abundant rainfall from April to October reduces the efficacy of spray fungicides. Earlier experiments showed that IBP (0,0 - Diisopropyl - S-benzyl

thiophosphate (IBP) 10% G) granule was the most effective fungicide to control blast.

This experiment in 1980 kharif investigated the effect and cost of an application schedule of IBP granules.

Six doses of IBP granules were dispersed by hand between rows in two equal applications (at tillering and at panicle initiation). Standing water (5-6 cm) in the paddy was maintained for 6-7 days. All treatments gave significant neck blast control (see table). IBP granules at 3.74 kg a.i./ha was the most economical dosage (yield 19.24% more

than control). Higher doses of IBP granules gave better neck blast control but without significant increases in yield. ■

IBP granule effect on neck blast incidence and grain yield of IR8 at Nagaland, India.

IBP granules (kg a.i./ha)	Neck blast infection (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
2.50	35.4	3.96
3.74	37.1	4.40
5.00	32.7	3.81
6.24	28.8	4.28
7.50	25.6	4.04
8.74	31.9	4.08
0 (control)	52.3	3.69
CD at 5%		0.36